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Decoupling the effects of varying amplitude and frequency in the electrical stimulation of optic nerve fibers

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Abstract: *Introduction.* Computational models of optic nerve stimulation can allow to estimate the neural response of optic nerve fibers electrical stimulation and thus can be exploited to tune stimulation parameters to obtain a specific target perception. In principle, such tuning should be performed in an automatic way, so that the chosen stimulation parameters minimize some given cost function related to the quality of resulting the visual perception, but the use of such automatic methods is still under study and no satisfactory solution is available yet. In the absence of automatic methods, stimulation parameters are customarily set via manual tuning, which can be extremely time-consuming if performed in a non-principled way. *Methods.* We build biophysically-accurate hybrid models of monopolar and bipolar electrical stimulation of optic nerve fibers to study how the fibers firing rates depend upon the stimulation parameters. *Results.* In the case of monopolar sinusoidal stimulation of optic nerve fibers, we show that the amplitude of stimulation controls the size of the recruited cluster of fibers, and that the frequency controls their firing rate, independently. Instead, for bipolar stimulation, we show that when cross-talk is non negligible it is very difficult to obtain rules of thumb linking the firing rate of target fibers to stimulation parameters. *Conclusion.* We show that, if the stimulation amplitude is kept such that neighboring stimulating sites do not produce cross-talk, it is possible to reconstruct visual scenes “pixel-by-pixel” without needing any optimization process. If on the contrary current steering is required and cross-talk is non negligible, then it is very difficult to obtain rules of thumb and the development and use of automatic optimization techniques should be preferable.

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1 Introduction

The electrical stimulation of the optic nerve has been proposed as a technique for vision restoration in patients in which retinal stimulation [1] is not a feasible option, for example because they suffer from extremely severe forms of retinal degeneration, which make retinal electrical stimulation ineffective. Optic nerve stimulation (ONS) is a less invasive alternative than cortical stimulation [2], as it does not require to pierce the skull, and because it interacts with a structure that has no function in a blind patient, while it is known that each area of the cortex is involved in multiple functions, even neglecting cortical reorganization after vision loss [3]. Finally, ONS is particularly promising as it has the potential to produce phosphenes spanning the whole visual field [4], it has been recently claimed that an increased visual field leads to a more useful vision restoration than increasing resolution in a narrow part of the visual field [5]. On the contrary, retinal and cortical stimulation are intrinsically limited by technological constraints to restore vision in a very restricted part of the visual field [1].

Computational models can help to design stimulation protocols as they allow to estimate the neural response to electrical stimulation without the need of experiments, with all the related ethical and economical costs. While the applied stimulation should ideally be automatically optimized, the problem of defining and solving such optimization problem is still under investigation and no fully satisfactory strategy has been proposed yet. Manual tuning of stimulation parameters is still the most frequent alternative when electrical stimulation is applied. Such tuning is extremely time consuming and has the potential to be greatly accelerated by the insight that can be gained from computational models.

Here, we show how in a few of in silico experiments how we can draw a set of guidelines and principles to guide manual or automatic open-loop (non-optimized) tuning of the parameters for optic nerve electrical stimulation.

2 Methods

2.1 Optic nerve fiber model

The model of optic nerve fibers has been taken from [6], [7]. Such model belongs to the family of compartmental single-cable neuron models, where myelin is represented as completely insulating, and nodal membrane dynamics are modelled through Hodgkin-Huxley-like mechanisms, including persistent and transient sodium and potassium channel dynamics. We modelled 31 Ranvier nodes, with the 16th node placed at the level in which the stimulating sites are located, and recorded the membrane potential at the 26th membrane potential, checking that at that distance from the stimulation plane the stimulation waveform did not affect substantially the membrane potential evolution, which was thus only modified by travelling action potentials from the stimulated part of the fiber. All modelled fibers had diameter of 1 μm , which is a typical value for optic nerve fibers.

2.2 Simulation experiments

We performed three types of experiments. In the first two experiments, we considered monopolar stimulation (applied

through a single stimulating site), while in the last experiment we focused on bipolar stimulation (two stimulating sites acting concurrently). In all cases we imagined that the ground contact was placed very far from the stimulated region, as it is customary in stimulation experiments. Applied stimulations consisted of sinusoidal current injections with varying amplitudes and frequencies. For the first two scenarios, we considered fibers at varying distances, while in the last scenario we considered one fiber placed in the midpoint between two stimulated sites at a distance of 1 mm one from the other.

The extracellular potential at a given point was computed assuming a purely resistive, infinite, homogeneous, anisotropic medium with zero potential at infinity. These assumptions are appropriate as the human optic nerve is not fasciculated (homogeneity) but contains fibers (anisotropy).

3 Results

In **Figure 1**, we can see that fibers stimulated with a single sinusoidal current can exhibit a very limited range of behaviours, and that these behaviours are controlled in a simple way in terms of the amplitude of the stimulation and of the distance between the stimulating site and the fiber. At a given amplitude of stimulation, if we move away from the stimulating site, we encounter decreasing firing rates, while increasing the amplitude of stimulation also increases the resulting firing rate. What is interesting is that these variations in the firing rate happen in jumps, and that the obtained firing rate levels seem to be multiples of the stimulation frequency.

Figure 1. Dependency between firing rate, stimulation amplitude and fiber to site distance for different stimulation frequency values. Each point represents a simulation of monopolar sinusoidal stimulation. The color of the points represents the resulting firing rate. In total, 5,000 simulations for each subplot have been run.

Moreover, we notice that most of the fibers exhibit a firing rate which is double the stimulation frequency. Finally, increasing the stimulation amplitude, mostly contributes to increasing the fraction of activated (recruited) fibers at the dominant firing rate, which can be seen in the figure as the movement of the fiber-site distance threshold separating null and non-null firing rates.

In **Figure 2**, we can see that this “quantization” of the firing rate is a general phenomenon. Indeed, we can see that most of the simulations produced either null firing rate (inactive fibers), or a firing rate equal to the stimulation frequency, or one equal to twice the stimulation frequency, which is coherent with what we observed from **Figure 1**. It is possible to observe that several points fall outside of the three lines corresponding to inactive fibers, firing rates equal or twice the stimulation frequencies. These points could be the effect of some numerical instability in our methods, so that in reality the only possible frequencies are integer multiples of the stimulation frequencies.

In **Figure 3**, we show the results of the analysis performed with two sites stimulating at different frequencies. We can see that the results are not expressible in straightforward way in terms of simple laws and rules of thumb. For example, we can see that if we fix one of the two frequencies, the relation between the firing rate and the other frequency is not linear, and that the dependency between the two is less and less marked the higher the “fixed” frequency. The firing rates resulting from the stimulation from both sites at the same frequency are often substantially higher than the firing rates obtainable when one of the two frequencies is slightly perturbed, and the ratio between the firing rates and the common stimulation frequency has a tendency to increase with increasing stimulation frequency. We remark that further convergence analyses should be carried on to ascertain that all of the observed phenomena carry no dependency upon the integration time step and are not spurious relationships due to numerical errors.

4 Discussion

In the present work, we performed a set of simulations of electrical stimulation of optic nerve fibers to extract a set of rules of thumbs that can be applied to design stimulation protocol for vision restoration. While automatic optimization with a high-level function objective function (e.g. similarity between the supposed perception and the target visual scene, or even the similarity between cortical activations cause by the applied stimulation and the target scene [8]), several methodological and technical advance are still required before

Figure 2. Dependency between firing rate and stimulation frequency for monopolar sinusoidal stimulation. Each point represents a simulation, 5,000 total simulations have been

a satisfactory implementation may be proposed. The availability of simple rules relating the electrical stimulation parameters with the resulting patterns of neural activation will allow to produce open loop stimulation protocols, similar to the ones proposed for tactile sensory feedback in [9] and [10].

Here, we showed that when stimulating from a single site, the stimulation amplitude mostly controls the recruitment of the fiber population (namely the proportion of fibers that are activated by the stimulation), while the stimulation frequency controls the firing rate of the recruited fibers. This observation also provides some guide in preventing cross-talk between two stimulating sites: in fact, it is sufficient to choose stimulation amplitudes such that the cluster of fibers recruited by site 1 alone does not intersect with the cluster of fibers recruited by site 2 alone. Once the amplitudes are set, the stimulating frequencies can be chosen independently, driving the two clusters of fibers towards different firing rates. It is still possible that there may be a set of fibers between the two stimulating sites that are not recruited by the fields of each of the electrode sites alone but they are recruited by the superposition of the two fields: further simulations that we do not show here for limits of space confirm that such phenomena are marginal.

What said above allows to produce manually stimulation protocols in which the resulting percept is build “pixel by pixel”, where a pixel corresponds to a stimulating site. Thus, the number of implanted sites determines the achievable resolution and limits which visual scenes can be satisfactorily reproduced. This is a particularly severe limitation as the interfaces routinely implanted in nerves have very low stimulating site counts, typically in the order of few tens. It is currently possible to reach approximately one hundred sites using Utah arrays, but further increases in site counts are not

currently available and it is not clear how much it will be possible to increase in the next few years.

An alternative to achieve “super-resolution” is to use current steering, or to exploit cross-talk effects to produce non trivial electric field configurations. Here, we show that while the effect of superposition of two sources with different frequencies is reasonably smooth with respect to variations in such frequencies, it is not evident how we should proceed to extract rules of thumb to design the electrical stimulation to obtain a certain pattern of neural activation. When the superposition between several sites is required, true optimization techniques should be employed. On this respect, an extremely relevant step would be the definition of machine learning-based surrogate models that may enable us to predict the firing rate of fibers under multipolar electrical stimulation at a fraction of the computational cost of biophysically accurate models, similarly to what we have proposed in [11].

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Figure 3. Dependency of firing rate upon values of the independent stimulation frequencies of two stimulating sites equidistant to a nerve fiber. (Left) Full tridimensional plot of the firing rate surface for all the 625 frequency combinations. (Right) Dependency upon one of the two stimulation frequencies when the second is kept fixed at a given value.